

Updated report on user requirements and service design

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1. Abstract /publishable summary

This document is an update of Deliverable 1.1 - First version of the user requirements document. It describes the second round of meetings between AQ-WATCH partners and prime users in the USA, China and Chile (documented in Deliverable 6.1), and the first meeting of the Core Stakeholder Network (Core SN). It compiles the feedbacks and requirements from those prime users for the products that will be developed, and suggestions from the members of the Core SN.

The AQ-Watch products are developed based on the “spiral process”, in which the developers dynamically interact frequently with the prime users from the three target regions. The process will be modulated by the input of these users and will involve consecutive iterations with the objective to add values to the respective product/service. The feedback collected will be analysed and included in the new development. With the establishment of Core SN, the feedbacks from the network will also be included in this process.

2. Conclusion & Results

Not relevant

3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in section 1.1 of the Description of the Action:

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
[1] To design and produce new global and regional air pollution atlases that include the climatological distribution of chemical pollutants complemented by quantities such as the diurnal and seasonal variations, air quality and related health indices, premature mortality exceedance frequency, long-term trends, etc.	Yes
[2] To develop software packages with the capability to provide more accurate daily forecasts of air quality at the regional scale including tailored high-resolution fire smoke and wind-blown dust forecasts; downscaling of air quality forecasts to 2 km resolution in urban areas.	Yes
[3] To develop a source apportionment service to mitigate air pollution and hence increase the life expectancy of the population in different regions of the world, with special focus on the role of agricultural sources of air pollution and the potentially important effects of fracking operations.	Yes
[4] To develop a new tool-box that will be user-friendly and accessible to decision-makers to evaluate the efficiency of proposed mitigation measures in different industrial sectors on the resulting level of air pollutants in three different regions of the world. This will establish the basis for their wider adoption and generalization.	Yes
[5] To co-design, co-produce and co-evaluate, for the first time, prototype products and services with prime users in three regions of the world chosen for their specific level of economic, social and environmental development.	Yes

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package.

Objectives of WP1	Relevance in this deliverable?
1.1 Identification of the User’s Needs and elaboration of the User Requirement Document	Yes
1.2 Identification of Improved Products based on Users' feedbacks	Yes
1.3 Identification of the final products for commercialisation consistently with the business model	Yes

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

At the production phase of the toolkit, the meetings of the prime users and Core SN were organised with the purpose of presenting the additional development of the products, gathering feedback and other potential needs. The meetings with the prime users took place in Colorado, USA (online), in Beijing, China and in Santiago, Chile (online), while the meeting with the Core SN was conducted through webconference with Microsoft Teams. During the meetings, the 5 AQ-WATCH product modules were demonstrated and specifically those of concern to the corresponding were discussed in greater detail. The conversation focused on the feedback of the prime users and the stakeholders, and on the potential improvement of the products to attend their specific needs.

The outcome of these meetings and the information provided by the prime users and the Core SN members are important input to the product development. The information gathered during these meetings is being discussed among developers within the project, and will be the basis for further developments of the products and services. Similar consultations will happen within the year with a version of the prototype products and services in a more operational condition.

4.1 Feedback from the prime users in the 3 target regions

4.1.1 Feedback from prime users in the USA

The second meeting with prime users in Colorado, USA took place online on 1st February 2021, between AQ-WATCH partners from NCAR and Breezometer, and members of the Colorado Department of Public Health and Environment (CDPHE). CDPHE’s main tasks as they relate to AQ-WATCH are to (1) issue air quality warnings, daily during ozone season (June-September) and as needed other times; (2) issue permits for prescribed and agricultural fires; (3) provide air quality assessments for Colorado; (4) develop emission control strategies to ensure attainment of the national health standards for ozone (the Colorado Front Range is classified as a non-attainment area for ozone); and (5) provide documentation for exceptional events (e.g. wildfires, stratospheric intrusions, dust storms) that lead to the exceedance of a criteria pollutant and influence the attainment/non-attainment status. For more details of this meeting please refer to Section 4.1.1 in Deliverable 6.1. The feedback from CDPHE is summarized below:

General feedback

Value of the products

- Value for the different tools is well approved and their design and layout are well received.
- The products are seen to be of great support for public outreach (e.g., air quality alerts are issued via email, Twitter, Facebook and also broadcast on media) and for media requests (“one-stop shop”).
- Historical products as well as the fracking tool may be interesting to the public.
- However, the public audience must be cautioned that this information, specifically from the fracking tool as this is a very controversial topic, is based on models and subject to uncertainties.

Functionality of the products

- Legends should be added to the maps.
- An option should be provided to users to download all the images at the same time (e. g. as one PDF) as well as to download individual images (e. g. as png).
- End users should be able to change the colour scales on the map and possibly for the line plots and the concentration range, which would allow a clearer indication of seasonal changes in pollutant concentrations and of extreme events such as fires.

Specific feedback for individual products

Module 1: Global and regional air quality atlas

- This tool is useful to tell which parts of the Colorado Front Range have the worst air quality (a frequent public and media question).
- Showing satellite data as well as surface observations and model re-analysis are of interest.
- The in-situ observations should be displayed on top of the maps that show the model output.
- The historical data should be available for as long back as possible. “People are interested in understanding how AQ changed over long periods of time, even 10 years”. Decadal time scales are useful for the historical perspective.
- Air quality information for the recent 4-5 days (consider as a default setting) in addition to forecasts would be useful.
- Having a (static) emissions layer (e.g., the anthropogenic emissions in the model) could be useful for decision-making but adding emissions is not a top priority.

Module 2: Air quality attribution and mitigation

- The source attribution tool should display the contributions of all different sources (e.g., also dust and wildfires) to PM2.5 (and other compounds). This means all sources should add up to the total concentrations (with non-tagged contributions defined as “Others”).
- To help understand the importance of transboundary pollution, it is desirable to display which countries/states/provinces are contributing the most to air pollution in Colorado.
- Interstate transport of CO from selected states (to be determined in collaboration with the CDPHE, ideally to be changed interactively by the user) would be useful.

Module 3: Dust and fire forecasting system

- It is useful to show the location of fires on the map but the best way to do so still needs to be decided. If fires are shown by icons, there should be an option to turn the fire icon off so that they don't obscure the model forecasts. It would be useful if something similar to InciWeb (<https://inciweb.nwcg.gov/>) can be implemented (InciWeb provides the fire perimeter but this might not be identical to the fire information used in the models).

- Solar radiation/cloud display is useful to assist in understanding of ozone chemistry and displaying wind vectors would assist with characterizing transport of pollutants.
- Dust and fire forecasts should be overlaid with masks showing where the visibility is less than 5 miles, which is the threshold for issuing advisory in Colorado (“If visibility is less than 5 miles in smoke in your neighbourhood, smoke has reached levels that are unhealthy” – refer to <https://www.colorado.gov/airquality/advisory.aspx#GenYearRound>).
- Visibility forecast would be also of value for Class 1 (e.g., National Parks) areas (U.S. EPA Regional Haze Program – refer to <https://www.epa.gov/visibility>).
- The domain of the dust and wildfires product should cover western US and western Canada.

Module 4: Fracking analysis

- This tool might not be used on a daily basis by CDPHE, but could be of a definite interest by the public.
- The tool should include a warning that the estimates, while to the best of knowledge and constrained by observations, are based on a model and therefore subject to uncertainties.
- The tool needs also to include additional information in layman's terms.
- The list of proposed VOC species looked sufficient to CDPHE.

Additional suggestions

- Regarding satellite imagery, CDPHE frequently uses GOES- 16/17 imagery (<https://rammb-slider.cira.colostate.edu/>), and would be seen as highly beneficial if added to the atlas (Module 1) in as close to NRT as possible to examine fire hotspots and dust outbreaks.
- The most frequently-used GeoColor (CIRA) and 7, 3.9 μ m and the recently-added Shortwave WindowDust - DEBRA (CIRA) product should be added as well.

4.1.2 Feedback from prime users in China

The second meeting with prime users in China (Figure 2) took place on 12th March 2021, between AQ-WATCH partners from the Beijing Municipal Institute of Labor Protection (BMILP) and members of the Taoranting Subdistrict Office (TRT). TRT’s main tasks as they relate to AQ-WATCH are to (1) Assist air quality monitoring, related assessments and information dissemination in the Taoranting sub-district of Beijing; (2) Establish, supervise and administrate the implementation of strategies to ensure attainment of air quality in Taoranting Street to the pollution reduction targets of Xicheng District. For more details of this meeting please refer to Section 4.1.2 in Deliverable 6.1. The feedback from the prime users is summarized below:

General feedback

Value of the products

- The design and layout were well-received and the system was found to be informative in regard to the distribution of air pollutants at various scales, source apportionment and prediction results. The user-controllable component of the system was also well-approved.
- As government users with a focus on the street level, the current situation and the impacts of governance measures of air quality on local scales are most concerned.
- The high resolution gridded local data and related source apportionment/mitigation module are of the most interest.

Functionality of the products

- Legends can be added to the maps to tell the user the specific concentration value range represented by different colours.
- The colour of the legend can correspond better to the air quality standard grade of the country.
- The users can choose the units of the species, such as ppb, ppm, or $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. For Chinese users, the default unit is best set as $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (mg/m^3 for CO) to conform with Chinese National Air quality Standards.
- The product is better to be multi-lingual, i. e. to at least include English and Chinese, in order to facilitate the use of non-English primer users like Chinese users.

Specific feedback for individual products

Module 1: Global and regional air quality atlas

- Meteorological parameters can be added to the maps, as well as a (static) emission layer to the air quality atlas layer, which will be easier for users to intuitively understand the source direction of pollutants and more useful for decision-making.
- It will be more helpful for air quality management if an automated warning alerts the user of high concentration events and informs on recommended mitigation measures. For example, a warning message could be sent automatically to the user's phone if the concentration of one or more pollutants exceeds the standards to remind him/her that one or more certain measures should be taken.
- Users also want to see the system to provide a set of high-resolution satellite observation data/maps.

Module 2: Air quality attribution and mitigation

- TRT was most interested in this module and believed it is very useful for their AQ management work.
- Apart from the species ($\text{PM}_{2.5}$, PM_{10} , NO_2 , SO_2 , CO) which have been included in the AQ mitigation module of the current prototypes, ozone (O_3) is also a species of interest. Specifically, TRT would like to know the contribution of air pollutants (especially $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ and O_3) that is due to traffic into the city versus local sources in the city.
- For the local sources, TRT would like to know which sectors are contributing the most in Taoranting as this information is needed to support their decision-making.
- The species are suggested to be kept consistent between different types of figures (e. g. mitigated pollutant levels, country contribution and sector contribution).
- "Country contribution" can be replaced by "spatial contribution" representing states, cities and districts in addition to countries.
- The figures and species shown on the panel of "historical" and "forecast" tab are different, which are better to be consistent.

Module 5: Air quality forecast

- Similar feedback as given for the products in Module 1 also apply here.
- The evolution of the meteorological situation overlaid on the forecasting air quality map can be included.

Additional suggestions

- Observed concentrations and emission data of carbon dioxide and other greenhouse gases such as those available from satellite would be a valuable addition to the maps in order to support China's carbon peak and carbon-neutral target.

4.1.3 Feedback from prime users in Chile

The second meeting with prime users in Chile took place on 15th December 2020, between AQ-WATCH partners from the University of Chile, Barcelona Supercomputer Center and Breezometer, and members of the Chilean Association of Renewable Energy and Storage (ACERA, in Spanish). Given the characteristics of the prime users, the workshop was centred on the Dust and solar energy forecasting product in Module 3. For more details of this meeting please refer to Section 4.1.3 in Deliverable 6.1. The feedback from ACERA regarding the Dust forecasting system is summarized below:

General feedback

- Dust forecasting tools are still little known in the Chilean market and specifically as it relates to the production of solar energy.
- Although solar power plants are working on monitoring and cleaning alternatives (e.g., soiling models or use of internal sensors) and dust forecasting instruments are generating more and more interest and demand, having access to dust forecasts would be more useful on a medium- and long-term scale than on a daily basis. This is explained mainly by two reasons that also illustrate the needs of the Chilean Solar Power market: 1) information related to the dust forecast can be linked with other relevant production data and used for planning purposes in e. g., costs associated to the energy losses due to dirt, the cleansing of solar panels, etc. ; 2) the dust activity in the Chilean desert is different from that in other countries. In Chile it is not common to have intense dust events as can be observed in other parts of the world (e.g., Saudi Arabia), so cleaning is not needed on a daily basis but rather something that can be planned.
- The information related to dust forecasting, such as the one proposed to be delivered through AQ-WATCH, would be most useful for the market (or pricing) department of the solar plants (where production is planned on a yearly basis), and not so much for the maintenance and operation departments. In other words, the needs of the Chilean market are not in regard to operations, but rather planning. Based on these results, *it is planned in the next meeting to invite participants that are related to the market and pricing areas and put less focus on the maintenance and operation sectors.*

Usefulness of dust forecasts

- The information provided would complement and allow working with the sensors already installed in the solar plants, which identify inefficiencies in temperature and availability.
- The data could indicate how much energy is being lost or, in other words, allow to balance between the loss in production due to energy loss (due to dirt) and cleaning costs.
- The information provided could allow optimizing costs in different aspects such as maximize production, cleaning costs and water consumption.
- The data could allow conducting site studies and characterize the cycles and times when cleaning of solar panels is most efficient and develop maintenance plans and costs accordingly.
- Having a monthly or annual product would be useful for the plants planning and construction stage, as it would estimate the approximate production in a year according to parameters such as the P80 probability of irradiation and P80 of dirt.

- A 7-day forecast could be useful for planification and distribution by the supply regulator of the electricity market.

Needs and expectations from ACERA

- The solar energy industry is still rather unfamiliar to dust forecasting, but there is a growing interest, mainly for its potential to support planning activities in different areas.
- An operation and maintenance system can be developed in which data and optimization calculations regarding energy loss can be integrated. In this way, a complementary analysis of the data could be done at the plant.
- In the area of operation, it is more important to have a model that is corrected according to the variations of 'a typical year', and that also allows the identification of external factors that may modify the dirt rate and the P80 model.

Suggested improvement to the platform

- For operation and maintenance, the platform format (colour maps) can be improved regarding the information on the energy lost.
- It would be useful if the information provided could allow a cross-over with the plant data.

4.2 Feedback from the Core Stakeholder Network

The first meeting of the Core Stakeholder Network (Core SN) was held on 12th May 2021 between the AQ-Watch partners from MPI-M, INEDEV and Breezometer, and other 14 Core SN members from 12 organisations in 9 countries. The list of participated organisations is shown in Table 1. The participants include representatives from international organisations with environmental protection advocacy, local governmental organisations on environmental management, and private companies involving environmental policies. The AQ-WATCH partners first presented a general overview of the AQ-WATCH project. The expectations to the Core-SN members from the consortium were also communicated. The 5 product modules were also demonstrated on the AQ-WATCH User Interface Platform. Following the demonstration, a discussion was organized and the first feedback from the stakeholders was collected. The main recommendations are summarized as the following:

Uptake of air quality monitoring information by the public

- Concerns were raised on how the general public are going to uptake the air quality monitoring information from the AQ-WATCH products.
- Yair Giwnewer from Breezometer indicated that Breezometer, in general, maximizes the effectiveness of information dissemination to the public by ensuring maximum accuracy of their products, maintaining high impacts of their products even for areas without much data surveillance, and providing the products at a relatively high-resolution (3 km) around the globe even in lay-back areas.

Localization of the product to address local issues

- A number of participants were interested in knowing how the AQ-WATCH products can address the small-scale air quality activities or effects.

- User tools are expected to be with higher spatial resolution to simulate local air quality scenarios so that the local policy makers can use this information to address local issues. For instance, a model with 400 m resolution is required to simulate the air quality activities in Delhi driven by the local weather.
- The capacity for the local scientists or officers to use the AQ-WATCH products should be explored in order to adapt the respective products to their local environments and needs.

Capacity building to use the AQ-WATCH tool

- Several participants stressed out the importance to ensure that the users of the system will have the capacity not only to use it but also to take decisions based on its results.
- The consortium should assess the needs for training sessions and/or consultancy services to accompany some clients.

Flexibility in application to areas with little data

- Many participants indicated the importance of the flexibility of the AQ-WATCH products for the application in different cities and regions, especially in areas where data (e.g. emission, satellite data, in-situ data) are scarcely available.
- It is also important that the products are also available and widely marketed in such areas, especially in the developing regions in Asia, Africa and Global South.

Importance of data for model/product validation

- Many participants agreed that the products should be well validated especially in areas with little data surveillance. A couple of suggestions included the use of in-situ data from low-cost sensors or mobile networks in the validation of the products.
- The AQ-WATCH partners encouraged the African participants to provide their available in-situ data to the AQ-WATCH group for product validation, on top of the planned validation activities with the three prime users. A metadata list can be included to record the inventory of currently available in-situ data alongside with the global/regional atlas.

Participating organisation	Corresponding country
Afriqair	Rwanda
Airqo	Uganda
Air Quality Consultants Ltd	United Kingdom
Air Quality Management Centre, Directorate in charge of environment	Sénégal
Health Effect Institute	United States
Hong Kong Environmental Protection Department	Hong Kong
Indian Institute of Tropical Meteorology	India
International Global Atmospheric Chemistry	United States
National Agency for Environmental Management	United States
RICARDO	United Kingdom
UN Environment Programme (UNEP)	Kenya
World Resource Institute	United States

Table 1: Participating organisations in the first Core SN meeting

5. Dissemination and uptake

5.1 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is

X	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This report is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

5.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

Although the content of this deliverable is public, it will be mainly used by AQ-WATCH partners and prime users, as described in the proposal. The product specification will be discussed with all partners and will be presented to prime users in the next meetings as part of the interactive process in order to further develop those products.

6. Deliverable timeliness

Is the deliverable delayed?

Yes No

Justification: Additional communication between a partner and the corresponding prime user is needed to clarify some of the prime user's needs. The preparation time of this report is therefore longer than originally planned. This delay will have no impact in further developments in the project.

7. Sustainability

Not relevant

8. Full track of dissemination activities

Not relevant

9. Full track of publications and IP

Not relevant